

TRADITION IN TURKIC LITERATURE**Rahmatova Govhar Omonovna,***Senior Lecturer, Department of Languages-1,**Al-Bukhari University,**Doctor of Philosophy in Philology (PhD)*

The didactic principle, that is, the call to morality, discipline, and perfection in the oral tradition of the Turkic peoples, also had a significant influence on the written literature of the later period. This can be seen by comparing the didactic in Makhmud Kashgari's "Divani lugati-t-turk" and the poems in Alisher Navoi's works.

If we look at the poems in the works of Alisher Navoi, we can see that the author effectively used the didactic ideas of folklore and developed them.

The oral tradition of the Turkic peoples and the teachings of Alisher Navoi condemn the evils of the people and glorify their good deeds; It combines similar aspects, such as the benefits of learning. Didactic promotes generosity, openness, humility, loyalty and compassion, forgiveness, humility, and greed, greed, materialism, anger and arrogance, hypocrisy, impatience, oppression, and violence.

One of the best qualities in human beings is patience. Patience is enduring suffering and affliction; voluntary restraint; to be satisfied. Both in the oral tradition of the Turkic peoples and in the works of Alisher Navoi, it is emphasized that these are good qualities¹.

For example, in "Divani lugati-t-turk":

Kelsä qalî qatîğliq,

Ertär teyü seriñil.

Ödläk işin bilip tur,

Anča añar tiräñil (DLT², 404).

¹ <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sabr>

² ДЛТ – Махмуд Кошғарий. Девону луғати-т-турк [Туркий сўзлар девони]. Нашрга тайёрловчи: Қ.Содиқов. – Т.: Фафур Ғулом, 2017.

Alisher Navoi advises both to be patient with the worries of the world and not to suffer in any difficulties:

*Ajab ranjeki, andin sa 'b yoq ranj,
Vale čekkän kišiniñ bahrası ganj (MQ³, 56).*

And again:

*Har kimki, qanāat tarafı nisbatı bar,
Barča el ara tavāze-u izzatı bar,
Ulkim tama-u hirs bilä ulfatı bar,
Yaxşı-yaman icrä zillat-u nakbatı bar (MK, 53).*

Navoi says that lack of patience can lead to suffering:

*Sabr azidin azāb, anduh köpidin iztirāb,
'Aškdin saylı balā, āh otidin har dam 'alam (BV⁴, 290).*

Among the examples of folklore, the most sung didactic poems are about learning and appreciating it. For example:

*Bilgä erig eđgü tutup, sözün ešit,
Erdämini ögränipän işqa sur-a.*

Do good to knowledgeable, intelligent people and listen to their words. Learn and practice science (DLT, 171).

Or:

*Alğil ögüt mendin, oğul, erdäm tilä,
Boyda uluğ bilgä bolup, bilgin ülä (DLT, 34-35)*

Alisher Navoi, in his book “Muhokamatu-l-lugatayn”, also calls for knowledge to be learned:

*Ilmdı āriy ulusniñ jähili xudkāması,
Örgänürgä jidd-u jahd etgän jahān allāması (MQ, 115).*

³ MQ – Алишер Навоий. Муқаммал асарлар тўплами. Йигирма томлик. Ўн тўртинчи том. Маҳбуб ул-қулуб. – Т.: Фан, 1998.

⁴ BV – Алишер Навоий. Муқаммал асарлар тўплами. Йигирма томлик. Бешинчи том. Бадоеъ ул-васат. – Т.: Фан, 1990.

There are also poems in didactic Turkic that encourage people to learn a profession. In “Divani lugati-t-turk” it is as follows:

*Sewünmägil yund, ügür, ađğır, anin,
Altun-kümüš bulnapan, ađı, tawar.*

Rejoice in the discovery of horses, thoroughbred horses, stallions and camels, as well as gold, silver and silk garments, and acquire a trade and art (DLT, 253).

We find the same teaching in the works of Alisher Navoi:

*Kim bolsa hunarsız işi – oq ranjı erür,
Bu vajh ilä hunarı ganjı erür (NJ⁵, 179).*

In Turkic oral poetry, politeness and openness are valued. Because these qualities are one of the pillars of human morality. Poems of the same content are included in the “Divani lugati-t-turk”. For example:

*Külsä kişi yüziñä,
Körklüg yüzin körüngil.
Yawlaq ködüz tiliñni,
Eđgü sawıđ tilängil.*

If someone laughs at you, look at him with an open face, be sweet-spoken, and treat him kindly, restrain your tongue (DLT, 338).

Navoi also advocates openness, emphasizing that generosity is more than generosity:

*Külär yüz ilä atā –
Saxā ustıđa saxā (MQ, 125).*

Navoi’s oeuvre includes issues such as hospitality and hospitality, which are one of the most important social etiquettes for the peoples of the East, as well as the oral tradition of the Turkic peoples. Hospitality is widely sung in the oral tradition of the Turkic peoples:

Körklüg tomuđ özünkä,

⁵ NJ – Алишер Навоий. Мукамал асарлар тўплами. Йигирма томлик. Ўн бешинчи том. Назм ул-жавоҳир. – Т.: Фан, 1999.

*Tatliğ aşiğ adınqa,
Tutğil qonuq ağırlığ,
Yađsun čawıñ bodunqa.*

He says, put on your beautiful clothes and share your sweet food with others. Be hospitable so that your fame may spread throughout the world (DLT, 32).

When a guest arrives, it is important not to be negligent:

*Kelsä qalı yarlığ bolup yunčığ uma,
Keldür anuq bolmiş aşiğ tutma uma.*

When a poor, helpless, poor guest comes, give the guest what you have [what you have] quickly, and do not delay and neglect the guest (DLT, 50).

Navoi also says that hospitality is a blessing:

*Mehmānnıñ mehrin asrağil jān ičrä,
Ne'mat qalın äylä xāni ehsān ičrä,
Har nečä adad öksük esä nān ičrä,
Barakat yetürür qalın ilik xān ičrä (NJ, 15).*

In the Turkic peoples, special attention is paid to openness and gentle nature (hilm). Because these are signs of goodness. It is said that one should be polite and open-minded to please and evaluate one's work:

Comparing the “Divani lugati-t-turk” and Alisher Navoi’s didactic, we have seen that the poetic passages, with their ideological and artistic aspects, cover and complement each other’s current topics.

In conclusion, Alisher Navoi in his didactic effectively used didactic ideas in the oral works of the Turkic peoples and developed them artistically.

References:

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5. <https://uz.wikipedia.org/wiki/Sabr>